

20 830m and 14 705w cm^{-1} in $\text{Mn}(\text{HL})_2$ and attributed to ${}^5A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (G) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (G) transitions, respectively, in an octahedral field⁸. The electronic bands of $\text{CuL.H}_2\text{O}$ observed at 21 740m and 15 150m cm^{-1} were assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transitions, respectively, in tetragonal field. Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes display one ligand field transition at $\sim 23\,200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transition similar to planar complexes⁷. The second transition observed in the uv region at $27\,020\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was attributed to ligand absorption.

The ir spectra of the ligand display ν_{NH} at $3\,140$ (isatin NH) and $3\,040\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (thioamide NH). In $\text{M}(\text{LH})_2$ complexes, the former is retained while the latter disappears indicating deprotonation of the thioamide (HNCS) moiety. In case of $\text{ML.H}_2\text{O}$ complexes, both the NH vibrations disappear suggesting the deprotonation of both the NH moieties due to complexation. A broad band at $3\,450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the aquo-complexes was attributed to ν_{OH} of water molecule. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of the free ligand was observed at $1\,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which shifted to lower frequency by $38-50\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\text{M}(\text{HL})_2$ and $\text{HgL.H}_2\text{O}$ complexes but it remained unaffected in Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes. The shift of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ to lower stretch suggest coordination of C=O oxygen to metal. In case of Cu^{II} complex, the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ almost disappears and a new $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band observed at $1\,260\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate that the C=O oxygen was coordinated to Cu by deprotonation in the enolic tautomer,

In case of the complex $\text{HgL.H}_2\text{O}$, the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band was observed at $1\,662\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating that the C=O oxygen being bonded to Hg^{II} in keto form and the disappearance of the isatin ν_{NH} suggest the coordination of isatin (NH) nitrogen to Hg^{II} through deprotonation. The deprotonation and involvement of the isatin part (NH) atom indicated the dimeric or polymeric nature of the complex. The aldimine (C=N) stretch of the ligand ($1\,630\text{ cm}^{-1}$) shifted to lower frequencies in almost all the complexes suggesting the involvement of C=N nitrogen in bonding with the metal atom¹⁰. The thioamide bands I, II and III of the ligand located at $1\,542$, $1\,356$ and $1\,140\text{ cm}^{-1}$ shifted to higher frequencies, while the thioamide band IV (890 cm^{-1}) shifted to lower frequency in the complexes by 200 cm^{-1} , indicating the bonding of deprotonated thiol (SH) in almost all the metal complexes^{8,9}. The new bands observed in the far-ir region $640-605$, $470-434$ and $420-335\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of the complexes were tentatively assigned to M-O, M-N and M-S stretches, respectively¹⁰⁻¹². Thus on the basis of the foregoing discussion it is inferred that the ligand offered

terdentate (O, N, S) chelation to Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cu^{II} , Co^{II} and Hg^{II} while bidentate (N, S) chelation in Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} in the complexes. In case of Hg^{II} complex, isatin part (NH) is also involved in bonding and completing the coordination number four to Hg^{II} .

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Complex Formation with some Bidentate Ligands. Part-II. Stability Constants of Complexes of *vic*-Hydroxyaldoximes with Manganese(II), Cobalt(II) and Zinc(II)

C. K. BHASKARE* and P. P. HANKARE

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 001 and

R. S. RAMPURE

Department of Chemistry, Sangameshwar College, Solapur-413 001

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In this paper we report the deprotonation constants of oximes of substituted-salicylaldehydes and formation constants of their complexes with Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} in water-ethanol (50%, v/v) medium.

Experimental

Salicylaldoxime (SAO; AnalaR) was used as such. Other *vic*-hydroxyaldehydes were prepared by standard procedures^{1,2}. 3-Methylsalicylaldoxime (3-MSAO), 5-methylsalicylaldoxime (5-MSAO) and

5-bromosalicylaldehyde (5-BSAO) were prepared by refluxing the respective aldehyde with hydroxylamine hydrochloride³. The products obtained were recrystallised from ethanol. A standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (AnalaR) solution⁴ (0.98 M) was used as the titrant.

The dissociation constants of the ligands and their formation constants with Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} were determined in the water-ethanol (50%, v/v) medium at ionic strength 0.1 M and temperature 25° by potentiometric titrations as described earlier⁵. The results are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS WITH SAO AND ITS SUBSTITUTED DERIVATIVES

Ethanol-Water = 50% (v/v), Ionic strength = 0.1 M (NaClO₄), Temp. = 25°

Cation	Constant	SAO	3-MSAO	5-MSAO	5-BSAO
H ⁺	log K_{OH}^H	10.60	10.82	11.15	9.89
	log K_{NOH}^H	12.73	12.69	12.75	12.65
Co ^{II}	log K_1	6.90	7.02	7.41	6.70
Mn ^{II}	log K_1	6.09	6.02	6.77	5.89
Zn ^{II}	log K_1	5.67	5.71	6.28	5.68

Results and Discussion

In all cases the stability constant values follow the order, Co > Mn > Zn. A comparison of the stability constant values of salicylaldehyde and its substituted derivatives with the corresponding values for complexes of the substituted-salicylaldehydes⁵ reveals that log K_1 values for ligands of (NO⁻) type are always higher than that for the ligands of (OO⁻) type.

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Complex Formation with some Bidentate Ligands. Part-III. Solution Equilibria in the Complex Formation of Bivalent Metal Ions with Thiosemicarbazones of *vic*-Hydroxy aldehydes

C. K. BHASKARE* and P. P. HANKARE

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004 and

R. S. RAMPURE

Department of Chemistry, Sangameshwar College, Solapur-413 001

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THE pharmacology of thiosemicarbazones and their complexes has expanded dramatically since its initiation¹ in 1946 in the study of antitubercular activity. There has been considerable research in the field of physiological activity of the ligands and their ability to form chelates with metals. But no significant investigation has been made about the properties of the complexes in solution. The present paper deals with the formation constants of the complexes of Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (SATSC), 3-methyl salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (3-MSATSC), 4-methyl salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (4-MSATSC), 5-methyl salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (5-MSATSC) and 5-bromosalicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (5-BSATSC) using Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium maintaining a constant ionic strength, $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄) at 25° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).

X = H, 3-CH₃, 4-OH, 5-OH, 5-Br.

Experimental

The thiosemicarbazones of salicylaldehyde were prepared by refluxing 3-CH₃-salicylaldehyde, 4-CH₃-salicylaldehyde, 5-CH₃-salicylaldehyde and 5-Br-salicylaldehyde with thiosemicarbazide. For synthesis of thiosemicarbazones general procedure² of condensation was used with certain modifications. The products obtained were recrystallised from ethanol. Carbonate-free NaOH (AnalaR) solution³ (0.98 M) was standardised with succinic acid. A 4 M sodium perchlorate (E. Merck, G.R.) solution was used for adjusting the ionic strength. A 70% perchloric acid (E. Merck, A.R.) solution was diluted with distilled water to obtain 2.0 and 0.2 M solutions. Solutions of the ligands (0.04 M) were prepared in ethanol. Metal perchlorate solutions were prepared by treating 20 ml of 2 M HClO₄